

A REVIEW ON PREVALENCE, CAUSES, AND TREATMENT STRATEGIES OF HAIR FALL AMONG MEN AND WOMEN

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ABSTRACT

Hair loss is a problem associated with various causes, including dietary deficiency, stress-related imbalance of hormones, and scalp conditions such as psoriasis, dandruff, and seborrheic dermatitis. The major association of hair fall is between deficiency of D3, iron, and imbalance of thyroid hormones, with the diffusion of hair loss, especially in the youth population. The hair loss is also based on chemical treatment, styling products, and serums. The COVID-19 pandemic has been a significant benchmark for hair loss over the last five years. Treatment and prevention of hair loss by means of Ayurvedic formulations - oils, masks, blends, and synthetic treatments such as minoxidil and hair transplantation are elaborated along with their potential side effects. Statistical analysis, like the chi-square test, evaluates the effectiveness of topical treatments, chemical and natural formulations in hair loss. Important hair type traits and management strategies for reducing hair loss through nutrition, yoga, and supplements all work together to reduce stress-

induced hair loss. However, thorough studies are needed for conditions like Telogen Effluvium (TE), Female Pattern Hair Loss (FPHL), and Chronic Telogen Effluvium (CTE), as well as methods for diagnosing and treating them.

KEYWORDS: *hair fall, dandruff, ayurvedic oil, vitamin D3, minoxidil, Covid-19, alopecia.*

INTRODUCTION

Structure of Hair

Hair is mainly composed of keratin, a fibrous protein consisting primarily of polypeptide chains. These chains are formed by amino acids linked by peptide bonds and are coiled into an alpha helix structure.^[1]

Hair consists of two major parts: the part beneath our skin, called the follicle attached with the root, which regrows hair; and above the skin surface, the shaft, which is the hard filamentous part extending above the skin (composed of multi-layer keratinized or flat dead cells) made up of keratin—the cuticle, which consists of flat, thin cells, and the cortex, which has keratin bundles in a rod-like structure. The medulla contains a disorganized open area at the centre of the hair.

The human scalp contains around 100,000 hair follicles, each undergoing cyclical phases of growth (anagen), regression (catagen), and rest (telogen). Significant hair fall occurs due to disruptions in these cycles. Several types of bonds contribute to hair's properties, determining its strength, flexibility, and texture.^[8] The following table provides details about the types of bonds and their roles in hair properties.^[6]

Type of bonds and their roles

Table 1.

Type of bond	Description	Role in hair properties
Hydrogen bonds	Found between the alpha-helix coils and are weak in structure, can be easily broken by heat or water.	35% of hair strength and elasticity.
Di-sulphide (Cysteine Bonds)	Cross-links between polypeptide chains are perpendicular to the axis of the hair nature.	Very important for toughness and enables permanent waving
Sugar Bonds	Helps retain moisture and is perpendicular to hair.	Toughness and strength of hair by locking in moisture

Functions of hair

The common causes of hair loss

Hair loss is a multifactorial condition influenced by hormonal, environmental, hygiene, lifestyle, and genetic factors.

Telogen effluvium is a temporary condition that leads to excessive hair shedding due to stress, illness, or poor nutrition, whereas androgenetic alopecia is a hereditary form of hair loss caused by hormones, affecting both men and women. Other conditions, such as alopecia areata, an autoimmune disorder, and tinea capitis, a scalp fungal infection, contribute to hair thinning and patchy hair loss. Moreover, traction alopecia results from tight ponytail hairstyles and excessive hair treatments, while scarring alopecia causes permanent damage due to inflammatory skin conditions.

Genetics plays a crucial role, particularly in pattern baldness. Hormonal imbalances—including high androgen levels, thyroid disorders, polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), and menopause—can significantly contribute to hair loss. Nutritional deficiencies, especially in women, such as lack of iron, biotin, vitamin D, zinc, and protein, weaken hair structure and bonds, leading to increased shedding. Scalp conditions like dandruff, seborrheic dermatitis, psoriasis, and fungal infections further impair follicle health, especially in allergic patients. Chronic stress, anxiety, and depression, notably during the COVID-19 pandemic, have been linked to increased hair fall and reduced hair density. Additionally, the use of chemical treatments, hair dyes, heat styling tools, and harsh hair products can cause breakage and thinning.

Autoimmune diseases like lupus and certain medications, including chemotherapy, antidepressants, and blood pressure medications, can directly impact hair health. Addressing hair loss requires a holistic approach, encompassing scalp care, a nutrient-rich diet, stress management, and the avoidance of chemical hair treatments.

A] Nutritional factors and their influence on hair loss

For healthy hair growth, a well-balanced diet that includes key nutrients is essential. Nutrients such as zinc, iron, lysine, selenium, and vitamins contribute overall health of hair follicles.

The intricate biological process of hair growth is unique to every individual. Hair growth is a complicated process that can be influenced by a number of factors, such as hormones and heredity. Hair follicles are metabolically active and need nutrients for growth and maintenance.^[9]

Deficiency of vitamins and nutrition could lead to disruption of the hair growth process, hair thinning, and excessive shedding.

Regulation in nutrition is required, as excess supplements can cause an imbalance.^[7]

To diminish deficiency and create balance is vital for maintaining hair health. Iron plays a significant role in transporting oxygen, which is required for supporting metabolic activities and is essential for hair follicles. In women, low iron levels are a common occurrence due to menstruation and a diet that causes hair loss. Ferritin is a form of iron that is stored in the human body; if excreted causes hair loss.^[9]

Zinc is a mineral that is essential for enzymatic reactions, which enhance cell growth and follicle repair. Deficiency of zinc can cause low growth by creating a discrepancy in the telogen phase, resulting in alopecia areata, increased hair shedding, and baldness.

Amino acids are necessary for many functions in the body for many functional and structural formations; Lysine is one such amino acid that aids in absorption and utilization for the density of hair.^[9]

B] Association between levels of vitamin D and hair fall among the youth

A deficiency in Vitamin D3 was found to be a major contributor to hair loss. A notable correlation between Vitamin D3 and hair shedding established D3 as an essential molecule for the diffusion of hair loss, as it regulates the hair follicle cycle from the telogen (resting) phase to anagen (growth) phase. Insufficient sun exposure and poor diet can lead to decreased Vitamin D levels, which are directly linked to conditions like telogen effluvium.^[7]

C] Levels of T3, T4, and TSH in diffuse hair loss in adult females

If an individual has hair loss that does not have any root or apparent cause, it might be due to low ferritin levels and thyroid hormones (T3, T4, and TSH) levels.^[8]

The disturbance in thyroid function, which causes hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism, can cause hair loss; even a mere imbalance or elevation in TSH can cause severe thinning, reduced hair volume, and brittle hair. In hypothyroidism, hair becomes coarse and fragile; notably, hyperthyroidism can cause excessive shedding and also irritation of the scalp. It is necessary to regulate hormone levels to restore hair growth and avoid unexplained hair loss.^[5]

Levels of serum ferritin and T3, T4, and TSH should be examined in all cases of diffuse hair loss without a perceptible cause, as iron deficiency and thyroid hormone disorders are the two common conditions often associated with diffuse hair loss, most of the time; an imbalance in thyroid levels can lead to a significant amount of hair fall.^[9]

D] Dandruff and its contribution to hair loss

Dandruff is a combination of both microbial and non-microbial factors

1. Microbial Causes - *Malassezia furfur* is a lipophilic yeast-like fungus on the scalp, which causes degradation of sebum triglycerides that turn into Fatty acid irritants (oleic acid), resulting in inflammation and flaking.

Staphylococcus epidermidis disturbs the scalp homeostasis and triggers dandruff^[13]

2. Non-Microbial Causes – Excess sebum production creates a favourable environment for the overgrowth of dandruff.

Dry scalp and environmental factors – cold weather, stress, pollution, and dehydration are the triggers for dandruff.

Hair products and cosmetics – high chemicals present in serums, shampoos, hair dyes, and styling products trigger dandruff.

Scalp conditions – Eczema, scalp psoriasis, and seborrheic dermatitis cause dandruff other symptoms may be irritation or dry scalp.^[13]

Prevalence of hair fall and factors that ascertain hair-related problems among men and women^[3]

Table 2.

Hair concern	Men	Women
Hair Fall	60.3%	72%
Premature Greying	37.97%	29%
Baldness	50.4%	29%
Dandruff	17.1%	22%
Post-partum hair loss	-	30%
Treatments /Serums	36%	62%
Use of Medications	59%	52%

Treatments for hair fall

A] Chemical treatments

1. Topical minoxidil 2% for mild to moderate female pattern hair loss (FPHL) without hyperandrogenism. Minoxidil – FDA-approved vasodilator (increases surface area of blood vessels) that prolongs the anagen phase.^[5]
2. Systemic antiandrogens like spironolactone, flutamide, and cyproterone acetate for FPHL with hyperandrogenism.
3. Finasteride is a 5-alpha reductase inhibitor used for baldness, usually in men.^[8]
4. Corticosteroids - to reduce alopecia areata and inflammation.^[6]
5. Peptide-Based Serums - Stimulate follicle activity and enhance the growth of hair by nourishing.

Table 3.

Condition	Treatment
Mild to moderate FPHL without hyperandrogenism	Topical minoxidil 2%
Mild to moderate FPHL with hyperandrogenism	Topical minoxidil 2% plus antiandrogens/finasteride
Mild to moderate FPHL with hyperandrogenism	Antiandrogens like spironolactone, flutamide, and cyproterone acetate
Mild to moderate FPHL with hyperandrogenism	Oral finasteride 1-1.25 mg/day ^[11]

Antifungal agents for dandruff reduction^[2]**Table 4.**

Chemical	Purpose
Zinc pyrithione	Stops fungal metabolism
Ketoconazole	Inhibition of ergosterol synthesis
Salicylic acid	Exfoliates the dead skin, resulting in reduction of flaking
Coal tar	Prevention of excessive shedding

B] Natural treatments

1. Application of Hair Oil, a blend of ayurvedic oils including Coconut Oil, Almond Oil, Jojoba Oil, Rosemary Oil, Argan Oil, Wheat germ Oil, Hibiscus Oil, Tea tree Oil, and Sesame Oil.^[5]
2. Aloe vera soothes the scalp and reduces inflammation.
3. Coconut oil strengthens follicles and prevents moisture loss.
4. Onion juice enhances blood circulation and reduces microbial growth.
5. Green tea is rich in antioxidants and promotes hair growth enhancement.
6. Castor oil is rich in ricinoleic acid, which increases hair density and volume.

To verify the safety and efficacy of natural remedies, statistical analysis has been carried out in healthy female subjects that suffered from dandruff induced hair fall; to demonstrate that natural treatment is effective in reducing hair fall, promoting hair growth, and alleviating scalp dandruff in healthy adult subjects, as hair loss and dandruff are common issues that Ayurvedic remedies may be able to address.^[14]

Another formulation of hair oil made from a mixture of different plants such as *Azadirachta indica*, *Semercarpus anacardium*, *Trigonella foenum-graecum* and *Ficus nucifera* oil for reducing hair fall by moisturizing the scalp, which promotes in healthy scalp resulting in volume and growth of hair.^[13]

Plants used for treating dandruff^[2]

Malassezia furfur and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* are major causes of dandruff, which leads to hair fall. The following table showcases the herbal alternatives for the reduction of dandruff.

Table 5.

Plant	Common name	Family	Part of plant used	Usage
<i>Piper bettle</i>	Paan	Piperaceae	Leaf	Juice of bettle leaves is applied on head for dandruff reduction
<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i>	Gurhal	Malvaceae	Flower	Grinded latex is applied for dandruff reduction
<i>Lawsonia inermis</i>	Mehndi	Lytharaceae	Leaf	Leaf juice is applied on scalp
<i>Datura metal</i>	Datura	Solanaceae	Fruit	Fruits grinded with water for application on scalp
<i>Mangnifera indica</i>	Mango	Anacardiaceae	Kernel	Kernels are made to paste with milk for application
<i>Nyctanthes arbor-tristis</i>	Har Singar	Oleaceae	Seed	Powder of the seed is spread on the roots of the hair evenly
<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	Tea	Theaceae	Leaf	Leaves are boiled with diluted lemon water for spraying
<i>Vitex negundo</i>	Chaste	Verbanaceae	Leaf	Leaves are boiled with suitable oil for application
<i>Citrus aurantofolia</i>	Nimbu	Rutuceae	Juice	Juice is mixed with castor oil for dandruff reduction

Chemical v/s natural topical treatments

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES

A cross-sectional study was conducted using simple random sampling to select participants from various families within the community. Both male and female subjects were provided with information about the study, and informed consent was obtained from all participants. Pilot testing of the interview schedule was carried out, leading to minor modifications. The administration of the schedule included the use of the PHQ-9 questionnaire, along with the collection of data on participants' weight, height, lifestyle, stress levels, and hair care habits. The statistical techniques employed in this study comprised the chi-square test, binary logistic regression, and descriptive statistics. Data analysis was performed using SPSS software version 11.5.

Chi-square tests and Mantel-Haenszel tests were utilized to evaluate the statistical significance of associations between various factors and hair-related issues. Additionally, 95% confidence intervals for prevalence rates and odds ratios were calculated using the Epi Info software package.

RESEARCH GAPS

- The analysis of hair fall was done on subjects and which did not involve any particular tests.

The study did not highlight other side effects of Vitamin D3 supplementation on hair growth; it didn't examine the role of other factors like anaemia, thyroid profile, and decreased serum ferritin, which have been linked to hair loss.

- Several botanicals such as *Piper betle*, *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis*, *Lawsonia inermis*, *Datura metal*, *Mangifera indica*, *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*, *Camellia sinensis*, *Vitex negundo*, *Citrus aurantifolia*, which have been claimed to have anti-dandruff activity in traditional hair care for the treatment of Dandruff, but scientific validation for most of the plants is lacking.
- The sample size of 30 subjects is relatively small; therefore, a larger sample population is needed in further studies to accurately assess the efficacy and safety of topical applications
- The nutrition deficiency gave an overview but didn't specify the items consumed through which the hair fall was decreased.
- The present scenario had a few limitations, such as having participants from the younger generation at a higher frequency. Despite the limitation, the current study delivers novel

outcomes on human stress and its impact on hair fall during the COVID-19 pandemic situation.

- Excessive supplementation of nutrients might show adverse effects.
- Lack of personalized treatment plans, one-size-fits-all treatments adopt a generalized approach rather than being tailored to individual hair types and the root causes.
- Inconsistency in results with natural remedies – While it is effective for some populations, natural treatments lack clinical validation and standardization of formulation.
- Side Effects of Chemical/synthetic Treatments – Minoxidil and finasteride may cause scalp irritation, dizziness, or hormonal disruptions and infertility.
- Limited Awareness of Nutritional Effect – Many individuals underestimate the role of diet and nutrient intake in hair health.
- Environmental Factors like Pollution and water quality play a significant role, so variation can change the desired outcome.

CONCLUSION

This review explores the critical factors that contribute to hair fall among diverse demographic groups, including men, women, and college-going individuals across various age groups.

Dietary habits and intake of supplements on a regular basis have been identified as significant contributing factors to hair-related problems. Particularly highlighting conditions such as hormonal hair loss in conditions like PCOD, PCOS, and postpartum hair loss in women. Inadequate nutrition and an imbalanced diet also contribute to hair loss. Maintaining healthy hair may require a nutritious and balanced diet and the prevention of excessive shedding. Both chemical formulations, like minoxidil and natural ayurvedic oils, are utilized for the growth of hair.

Statistical analysis for a deeper understanding of the association of hormones like T3, T4, TSH, estrogen and D3 emerged as a prominent factor of hair fall. The chi-square statistical test and other methods give a deeper insight into the correlations between factors and hair fall.

In conclusion, this review examines the key areas requiring attention to effectively reduce hair fall and enhance hair growth in daily routine through a combination of dietary, topical applications, and lifestyle interventions in various demographics.

Future trends

- Development of an Ai-based hair fall diagnostic system that can diagnose early issues and strategies for hair fall and curate personalized treatment.
- Designing regimes that do not have any adverse effect or any long-time effect for hair growth treatments.
- Curating quick and effective treatment that has a permanent solution for hair growth.
- Future comprehensive research is required to evaluate treatment – it's safety, efficacy and ensure validation before extending it to the masses

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